

Misinformation, Disinformation, and Autonomy: Against the Epistemic Paternalism Trap

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Abstract

Most tools developed to counter the issues of misinformation and disinformation at scale replicate the very problem they aim to solve. By filtering, flagging, and moderating content, such tools replace human judgment with algorithmic judgment rather than empowering the people navigating the information ecosystem. This is what we refer to as the epistemic paternalism trap. We argue that AI tools designed to address misinformation should function as scaffolds for epistemic autonomy — explaining their reasoning and supporting individual judgment — rather than as opaque arbiters that decide on the user's behalf. Three empirical and normative arguments converge on this conclusion. First, current algorithmic judgment is itself systematically biased and structurally less explainable than the human judgment it replaces. Second, correction-based ecosystemic interventions fail on two compounding grounds: they harm epistemic autonomy by substituting institutional verdicts for individual reasoning, and they fail on their own empirical terms, as their efficacy presupposes institutional trust that misinformation and disinformation have already eroded. Third, critical thinking education and transparency-oriented AI design better serve both epistemic autonomy and epistemic outcomes simultaneously — a convergence that holds even for those skeptical of autonomy's intrinsic value. We argue that AI tools designed to address misinformation and disinformation should function as scaffolds for epistemic autonomy — explaining their reasoning and supporting individual judgment — rather than as opaque arbiters deciding what information people should or should not access.

Introduction

Misinformation and disinformation threaten epistemic autonomy (Levy, 2021; Matheson, 2024; Wardle & Derakshan, 2017). This claim has become a near-consensus starting point in bioethics and public health communication, and for good reason: the capacity to form beliefs on the basis of reliable information, to evaluate evidence, and to make decisions that reflect one's genuine values is both a precondition for meaningful autonomy and a primary target of coordinated disinformation campaigns. The terms are not synonymous:

misinformation refers to false or inaccurate content circulated without deliberate intent to deceive; disinformation involves the intentional production and dissemination of false content to mislead (Wardle & Derakshan, 2017). The distinction matters for questions of moral responsibility and regulatory design. It matters less for the epistemic damage inflicted on individuals and communities: regardless of intent, false content degrades the information ecosystem, erodes trust in reliable sources, and impairs the conditions under which autonomous belief-formation is possible — an outcome referred to as epistemic pollution (Levy, 2018, 2021; Spitale et al., 2026). Unless the distinction between disinformation and misinformation bears directly on the argument, here we use misinformation as the default term throughout.

Misinformation threatens epistemic autonomy, but, as we will discuss, so do most of the tools developed to counter it at scale — platform moderation, content labelling, algorithmic filtering, automated fact-checking. They do so by attempting to fix the information ecosystem rather than by empowering the people navigating it, i.e., by removing, flagging, or reranking content. Anti-misinformation infrastructure can thereby replicate the very structure it aims to oppose. This is what we call the epistemic paternalism trap: the ethical problems of misinformation and the ethical problems of its remediation are, under this lens, structurally isomorphic.

The normative framework of this paper is autonomy-based. We draw on procedural accounts of autonomy as principled self-governance (Dworkin, 1988; O'Neill, 2002) and on social epistemology's analysis of epistemic agency and independence (Fricker, 2007; Zagzebski, 2012). We are explicitly pluralist about which conception of autonomy is at stake — non-interference, deliberative capacity, and epistemic independence are not equivalent, and the choice between them has direct implications for tool design. The foundational framework is process-centered rather than outcome-maximizing: the concern is not only whether individuals arrive at true beliefs, but whether they arrive at them through their own reflective capacities. We also argue, however, that the autonomy-oriented conclusion is supported by consequentialist reasoning under current empirical conditions — that protecting epistemic processes and producing better epistemic outcomes presently point in the same direction. That convergence is a strategic argument for the autonomy-oriented approach; it is not its foundation.

The standard defense of algorithmic systems is that they constitute a more reliable arbiter than unaided human judgment in misinformation-saturated information ecosystems. This response fails on empirical grounds. The algorithmic judgment substituted for human judgment carries its own systematic biases (Germani & Spitale, 2025; Motoki et al., 2024; Rozado, 2024), and these are less explainable than human biases (Boisseau, 2026), and therefore are also potentially less subject to correction and calibrated trust (Ferrario et al., 2020); furthermore, scholars of human-AI interaction have argued that trust in algorithmic systems should be incremental and calibrated to the degree to which we can verify the system's reasoning and track record (Ferrario et al., 2020); opacity forecloses exactly this kind of calibration (Boisseau, 2026). We are choosing between two sets of biases while trusting the one we understand less.

Here, we first examine empirical evidence suggesting that the misinformation problem is more severe than commonly assumed and that standard correction-based responses are structurally limited. We then present evidence for interventions strengthening the epistemic capacities of individuals rather than pursuing a "clean" information ecosystem, devoid of misinformation through algorithmic content moderation. We conclude by drawing out

implications for the design of AI tools, arguing that the normative commitments embedded in such tools must be made explicit, and that this requires a prior decision about which conception of autonomy the tool is designed to support.

The severity of the problem

The misinformation problem rests on a well-documented asymmetry, codified in Brandolini's law (also known as the Bullshit Asymmetry Principle): the energy required to refute false content is an order of magnitude greater than that needed to produce it (Brandolini, 2013; Williamson, 2016), and false content spreads significantly faster and more widely than accurate information (Vosoughi et al., 2018). It is commonly assumed that this gap is manageable through institutional fact-checking and platform governance (Saeidnia et al., 2026; Taguchi et al., 2023). Recent developments in generative AI, as we will discuss below, challenge this assumption on multiple fronts, and the assumption itself has rarely been subjected to empirical scrutiny (Broniatowski et al., 2025). In a controlled study comparing human-generated disinformation with AI-generated content, it has been found that false content generated by large language models (LLMs), when compared with human-generated content, is not only significantly harder to identify as false than human-produced content (Jakesch et al., 2023; Spitale et al., 2023) but also more persuasive (Goldstein et al., 2024; Spitale et al., 2023). The mechanism is not incidental: generative AI optimizes for fluency, coherence, and plausibility in ways that map directly onto the features that make content credible to human readers (Loru et al., 2025; Quattrociocchi et al., 2025). The tools that lower the cost of disinformation production do so precisely by making false outputs harder to detect. This difficulty is compounded by two distinct but reinforcing dynamics involving emotional content. At the level of production, emotional prompting (i.e.: instructing LLMs to generate content in emotionally charged registers) significantly amplifies the generation of disinformation (Vinay et al., 2025); at the level of reception, emotional framing is a functional feature of misinformation: content framed in emotionally charged terms activates cognitive heuristics that reduce critical scrutiny (Pennycook & Rand, 2019) and increase sharing behavior (Sun & Xie, 2026). These are distinct mechanisms, one concerns how AI can be prompted to produce more disinformation, the other concerns how emotional framing makes misinformation more effective once produced. Their combination creates a misinformation landscape that is qualitatively different from the one for which existing governance frameworks were designed.

It is against this background that the non-neutrality of algorithmic detection systems becomes particularly important. Evidence suggests that LLMs evaluate the same content differently depending on its declared source. For example, content attributed to Chinese sources has been shown to receive systematically lower credibility scores than equivalent content attributed to Western sources (Germani & Spitale, 2025). This has been referred to as 'source framing bias,' and reflects the social and epistemic asymmetries embedded in training data. When LLMs are deployed as components of detection tools or fact-checking systems, these asymmetries, these biases, and these assumptions become embedded into our epistemic infrastructure — and, crucially, under mistaken assumptions of neutrality we render them less visible and less contestable than the human biases they ostensibly replace. Source framing bias is just one instance of a broader pattern: LLMs exhibit systematic political and ideological biases in content evaluation (Motoki et al., 2024; Rozado, 2024), and demonstrate lower reliability precisely on contested factual claims, i.e. the category most relevant to misinformation (Saju et al., 2025). The problem is not merely that

algorithmic judgment is biased — so is human judgment. Nor is it that algorithmic systems are in principle unauditible: technical audits of model outputs are possible and increasingly mandated by emerging regulation (EU AI Act, 2024; Hartmann et al., 2025). The problem is epistemic. Algorithmic bias is structurally less legible to users than the biases of the human institutions it replaces. Users cannot easily interrogate a model's reasoning, nor can they calibrate their trust over time based on a visible track record. In many cases, they do not even perceive the process of algorithmic content filtering at all, as it operates without transparency and is designed to prevent certain information from ever reaching them. This opacity forecloses exactly the kind of calibrated epistemic deference that responsible reliance on expertise requires (Boisseau, 2026; Ferrario et al., 2020).

The failure of epistemic corrections

One model of misinformation response is correction-based: identify false content, produce accurate corrections, disseminate them through authoritative channels (Bateman & Jackson, 2024; Ecker et al., 2022) – or in alternative, after identification, limit the reach of the false information by preventing its spread. The model is epistemically intuitive: false beliefs should be displaced by true ones, and it is institutionally convenient, as it assigns the correction function to existing trusted institutional actors: public health agencies, scientific institutions, news organizations (Ecker et al., 2022; Lewandowsky et al., 2012). The limitations of this approach are increasingly acknowledged even at the policy level: reviews of counter-misinformation interventions consistently find uncertain effectiveness and context-dependency (Bateman & Jackson, 2024). The WHO guidance on infodemic management has further noted that infodemic management practices carry ethical risks, including erosion of institutional trust (Spitale et al., 2026; WHO, 2025). These concerns emerge from empirical evidence and from structural features of the correction model itself. Although debated, issuing corrections often entails further dissemination of the original misinformation, potentially exposing individuals who would not have encountered the false claim in the first place (Ecker et al., 2020; Mosleh et al., 2021). Beyond these limitations, here we argue that the epistemic correction model carries a more fundamental cost: it is structurally in tension with epistemic autonomy. In fact, correction-based approaches that adopt a binary true/false framework may cause epistemic autonomy harm: they substitute algorithmic and institutional verdicts for individual reasoning, habituating people to assess claims by outcome rather than by methodological process.

To explain this, let's take the notable Trump acetaminophen scandal from September 2025 as an example. President Trump, alongside Secretary of Health Robert F. Kennedy Jr., publicly urged pregnant women to avoid acetaminophen, citing an alleged causal link with autism despite the absence of established causal evidence (Pearson & Ledford, 2025; US Department of Health and Human Services, 2025). This claim sparked widespread criticism from medical societies and scientific institutions. Germani et al. have scrutinized these responses and argued that corrections that adopt a binary true/false framework and do not engage with the epistemic process by which claims should be evaluated fall short, and risk harming epistemic autonomy. Trump's claim was not certainly false; it was certainly *unjustified*, lacking the methodological grounding that warrants belief. By collapsing unjustifiability into falsehood, such corrections frame science as a contest of assertions rather than as a method of inquiry, habituating citizens to assess claims by verdict rather than by the reliability of the process that generates them. The harm to epistemic autonomy operates at the level of outcome: a correction that returns a verdict

rather than illuminating the reasoning behind it substitutes institutional or algorithmic judgment for individual judgment, and leaves people less equipped to evaluate future claims independently (Germani et al., 2026).

The verdict-based framing is not only epistemically problematic in principle; it also fails on its own empirical terms. As mentioned, corrections that repeat a false claim in order to refute it necessarily re-expose audiences to that claim, and repeated exposure can increase perceived familiarity, which functions as a proxy for truth (Fazio, 2020; Skurnik et al., 2005; Ye et al., 2026). The original backfire effect hypothesis, i.e. that corrections can paradoxically strengthen false beliefs by triggering defensive reasoning (Nyhan & Reifler, 2010), proved difficult to replicate at scale (Wood & Porter, 2019). The phenomenon, as originally described, appears less robust than initially claimed; yet the failure of corrections is not in doubt: even when they do not backfire, they frequently fail to produce durable belief change, decay rapidly over time, and struggle to reach the audiences most exposed to disinformation (Nyhan, 2021). The reason is structural: corrections do not fail because they are inaccurate or poorly communicated, but rather because they presuppose a high level of trust in the correcting institution within an already polluted information ecosystem (Germani et al., 2026; Hoes et al., 2024).

The structural logic is circular in a way that is difficult to break from within: misinformation systematically affects institutional trust; reduced institutional trust reduces the efficacy of corrections; reduced efficacy further erodes trust. We are, metaphorically, attempting to put out a fire with the water the fire has already evaporated. Correction strategies address symptoms rather than causes, and in doing so, they are inevitably reactive (Readelli et al., 2026), always operating in the aftermath of epistemic damage that compounds faster than corrections can follow. The structural failure of corrections compounds the epistemic autonomy harm identified above. Corrections create a form of epistemic dependency on institutional verdicts that turns out to be unreliable. An individual trained to wait for the correction rather than to evaluate the claim is left doubly disempowered: without the developed capacity to reason independently, and without a trustworthy external substitute. This is the deeper cost of designing for accuracy rather than for autonomy.

Building epistemic capacity as the primary intervention target

The preceding analysis suggests that interventions aimed at fixing the information ecosystem face structural limitations that cannot be overcome through technical refinement alone. An alternative intervention target emerges from a different body of empirical evidence. Mastery of critical thinking skills is among the strongest predictors of an individual's ability to recognize disinformation (Redaelli et al., 2025). The finding is significant for several reasons. First, it shifts the locus of effective intervention from the information ecosystem to the epistemic capacities of the person navigating it. Second, it identifies a protective factor that is in principle educable and transferable across domains, rather than content-specific. Third, it reframes the problem in terms that are more consistent with a robust conception of epistemic autonomy: the goal is not to ensure that individuals encounter only correct information, but to ensure that they are equipped to evaluate the information they encounter.

That said, traditional critical thinking education is a long-term, resource-intensive intervention that operates on a timescale incompatible with the pace at which misinformation events evolve and spread. This limitation (the timescale mismatch between education and rapidly evolving misinformation) is indeed an important one. There could be, however, a solution to this problem. Prebunking-based inoculation approaches (brief, online-deployable interventions that expose individuals to the techniques of manipulation before they encounter them) have demonstrated scalability across cultures and media platforms (Lewandowsky & van der Linden, 2021; Roozenbeek et al., 2020). Brief inoculation videos can be deployed as targeted content at scale, reaching large populations without the resource demands of formal education (Basol et al., 2021). The structural misinformation fingerprints framework (Readelli et al., 2026) is designed precisely to operationalize this: providing the specific manipulative patterns that prebunking can target, enabling a scalable, evidence-based curriculum for epistemic inoculation. We note that the inoculation studies cited here largely predate the current LLM-driven misinformation landscape. Whether prebunking-based approaches retain their effectiveness against AI-generated content at scale, and whether fingerprint-based curricula can keep pace with the generative capacity of frontier models, are open empirical questions that require dedicated investigation.

This reframing of the intervention target reflects a normative commitment to a particular conception of autonomy, one that locates agency in the capacities of the individual (Dworkin, 1988; O'Neill, 2002) rather than in the properties of the ecosystem (Ahlstrom-Vij, 2013). The distinction matters because it determines what kind of intervention is preferable. Filtering, labelling, and moderation protect individuals from false content by reducing their exposure to it; they are, in this sense, ecosystemic interventions that bypass individual judgment. On Dworkin's account, autonomy is not a matter of reaching correct conclusions but of exercising one's own capacity for reflective evaluation — the ability to assess, revise, and endorse one's beliefs through one's own reasoning (Dworkin, 1988). O'Neill draws a related but distinct contrast between principled autonomy, i.e. self-governance through reasons that are in principle shareable, and mere individual independence, which amounts to freedom from external constraint (O'Neill, 2002). Ecosystemic interventions may secure the latter while systematically failing to support the former: they seek to reduce exposure to harmful content without engaging the individual's capacity for principled judgment. This is precisely what Ahlstrom-Vij identifies (and defends) as epistemic paternalism: interference with an agent's inquiry conducted for the agent's epistemic good, but without the agent's engagement or consent (Ahlstrom-Vij, 2013). The “patronized” and the autonomous reasoner may arrive at the same belief; what differs is whether that belief was reached through the individual's own reflective process, or secured around it. Critical thinking education and prebunking, by contrast, operate through individual judgment: they aim to strengthen the capacity to evaluate, not to replace it (Lewandowsky & van der Linden, 2021; Redaelli et al., 2025; Roozenbeek et al., 2020; Siegel, 1990; Van Der Linden et al., 2020). Thus, we contend that ecosystemic interventions are structurally paternalistic, whereas critical thinking education and prebunking are structurally autonomy-promoting. The difference is architectural.

Implications for the design of AI tools

The argument developed so far has direct implications for how we design AI tools intended to support users in evaluating misinformation. There is a positive corollary: if the problem with existing AI tools is that they substitute judgment for individual reasoning, then the

design principle that follows is to build tools that do the opposite, i.e. that scaffold epistemic autonomy. The relevant design constraint should therefore be transparency of reasoning. A system that returns a verdict (true/false, credible/not credible) does something categorically different from a system that names the features of content that warrant suspicion, explains the structural patterns it has detected, and invites the user to evaluate its reasoning. One substitutes judgment, the other supports it.

From verdicts to scaffolds

The structural misinformation fingerprints framework provides the concrete basis for the design principle defined above. Misinformation carries structural fingerprints, i.e. recurring linguistic, narrative, logical, and critical thinking patterns that characterize manipulative content prone to virality (Readelli et al., 2026). The framework is explicitly content-agnostic: what makes misinformation recognizable to a trained reader is not that they know the relevant facts related to the contested claim, but that they can read the shape of the argument, its affective register, its logical structure, its misleading potential. If prebunking provides the methodological foundation for building resistance to manipulation (Van Der Linden, 2022; Van Der Linden et al., 2020), structural fingerprints provide the antigens that inoculation can target. The design implication follows directly. An AI tool built around this insight would not judge whether a given claim is true. It would rather identify the structural fingerprints that co-occur with misinformation across topics and make them visible to the user, not as a verdict, but as a basis for evaluation. In this sense, it would function as a scaffold for epistemic judgment rather than a replacement for it: teaching the reader to read the signs, rather than reading them on the reader's behalf without explainability or access to how the judgment was formed. This design choice reflects a prior normative commitment that must be made explicit before architectures are built. Ethical assessment of AI tools in the misinformation domain cannot be conducted solely through post-hoc auditing: it requires a prior decision about which values the tool is intended to promote, and which conception of the relevant value — in this case, autonomy — is to guide its design.

A potential objection: a tool that consistently highlights certain structural features as suspicious may function as a nudge toward a predetermined conclusion, differing from a verdict-issuing system only in form, a risk compounded by automation bias, i.e., the tendency to defer to algorithmic outputs as a heuristic replacement for independent judgment (Goddard et al., 2012; Skitka et al., 1999), documented even among users with high AI literacy (Carnat, 2024; Qazi et al., 2026). We contend that the objection misidentifies what makes algorithmic influence epistemically problematic. The concern is not directionality — testimony, expert opinion, and rational persuasion is directional — but opacity. A tool that names the structural features it has detected, and invites the user to evaluate them, makes its directional influence explicit and contestable. In this way, users can disagree with the tool's interpretation and retain final judgment. On Dworkin's account, what matters is whether the individual's own reflective process remains operative; on O'Neill's, whether the reasons offered are in principle shareable and open to scrutiny. A scaffold tool satisfies both conditions; a verdict-issuing tool satisfies neither. The difference is not cosmetic.

Not all ecosystemic interventions are equal

The preceding analysis groups platform moderation, content labelling, algorithmic filtering, automated fact-checking, and institutional corrections under the common heading of ecosystemic interventions. These tools differ significantly in their restrictiveness, forming a

spectrum from “hard” content removal, which forecloses access entirely, to “soft” content labelling, which preserves access and adds contextual information. They also differ in their epistemic architecture: human-supervised systems retain an element of accountable judgment, while fully autonomous systems remove it. These distinctions carry moral weight. Labels such as “disputed content” or corrections issued by fact-checkers are less paternalistic than invisible algorithmic demotion; more transparent still are labels that identify the specific structural features prompting concern, becoming less paternalistic and moving closer to the scaffold model described above. The argument developed in this paper does not hinge on how restrictive these interventions are, but on the structural logic they share: the substitution of individual judgment with ecosystem-level information management. The spectrum exists, and position on it matters; but occupying a less restrictive position on the spectrum does not escape the structural question of which conception of autonomy the intervention is designed to support.

Making normative commitments explicit

The concept of autonomy is not univocal, and its philosophical literature is extensive, and a full treatment falls outside the scope of this paper; for overviews, see (Christman, 2025; Matheson, 2024). Three distinct conceptions are nonetheless relevant here. Autonomy as non-interference grounds a minimal requirement: tools should not actively manipulate users' beliefs or restrict their access to information (Beauchamp & Childress, 2013). Autonomy as deliberative capacity adds a positive requirement: tools should support the conditions under which users can form beliefs through genuine deliberation — which includes providing transparent reasoning, not merely correct outputs (Dworkin, 1988). Autonomy as epistemic independence is the most demanding: tools should aim to increase users' capacity to evaluate information independently, reducing reliance on the tool itself over time (Zagzebski, 2012). Each of these conceptions permits a different range of design choices, and each forecloses others. Leaving the choice implicit does not eliminate it — it delegates the choice to engineers, to commercial incentives, or to the distributional biases of training data.

Is autonomy the right value?

The preceding argument has proceeded as though one question had an obvious answer: that autonomy is what matters here. It is worth pausing on this assumption. Ahlstrom-Vij's defense of epistemic paternalism rests on a different premise, i.e. that what we ultimately care about are epistemic outcomes rather than epistemic processes. On this view, if filtering produces truer beliefs than unmediated exposure to the information ecosystem, the autonomy cost is worth paying (Ahlstrom-Vij, 2013). The argument is not frivolous. Fallible reasoners in epistemically polluted ecosystems may reach better beliefs through well-designed ecosystemic interventions than through unconstrained deliberation.

Two answers are available. The first is normative, and it does not depend on the contingent limitations of current AI systems. Even granting the most favorable conditions for epistemic paternalism, i.e., reliable, unbiased algorithmic judgment, there remains a reason to prefer autonomy-supporting interventions. An agent whose true beliefs are secured by ecosystemic management (e.g., removing false or misleading information, moderating content, labeling, censoring, providing corrections, etc.) rather than through their own reflective capacities is epistemically dependent, and that dependence is fragile and subject to dynamics of fluctuating trust. The protective ecosystem may change; the belief-forming capacity, once developed, persists and transfers. Critical thinking skills (Redaelli et al., 2025;

Siegel, 1990), generalize across domains in ways that ecosystemic interventions cannot. This argument holds against a hypothetically perfect paternalistic system.

The second answer is empirical, and it applies to the tools as they currently exist. The case for epistemic paternalism assumes that the alternative to human judgment is a more reliable algorithmic one. However, as the evidence reviewed above shows, the algorithmic judgment being substituted for human judgment is not neutral. Large language models evaluate content differently depending on its declared source, independently of the content's actual quality (Germani & Spitale, 2025), and exhibit systematic political and ideological biases that distort content evaluation precisely in the domain where neutrality is most needed (Motoki et al., 2024; Rozado, 2024). If outcomes are what matter, the case for epistemic paternalism collapses because the paternalist's tools are themselves compromised. This objection is contingent: a proponent of epistemic paternalism could respond that the appropriate conclusion is to build better, less biased AI rather than to abandon the paternalistic framework. We do not dispute this possibility in principle. We note, however, that bias in systems trained on human-generated data is not a contingent engineering failure but a structural inevitability: as long as human judgment is itself systematically biased, the statistical regularities of training data will encode and propagate those biases. Patches and mitigation strategies can reduce specific, identified biases — but cannot eliminate the underlying reason as of why they exist in the first place. Even if this would be possible, granting a hypothetically unbiased algorithmic arbiter, the normative argument for epistemic autonomy would retain its force: the problem is not only that algorithmic judgment is biased, but that it substitutes individual judgment, undermining epistemic autonomy.

The two answers converge on the same conclusion under current conditions: protecting epistemic autonomy and producing better epistemic outcomes point in the same direction. One important caveat here is that the argument we developed assumes a public with at least some access to critical thinking education and with baseline epistemic capacities sufficient to benefit from scaffolding tools. For individuals and communities with low baseline information literacy, critical thinking skills, or with limited access to educational resources, ecosystemic interventions may be the only practically available protection in the short term. We do not contest this. Our claim is normative and structural, not logistical. Paternalistic approaches may be justified as a contingent and transitional response to epistemic vulnerability — but transitional means structured as such from the outset, with explicit conditions tied to the expansion of educational access, rather than as a permanent default that becomes entrenched through institutional inertia. The normative goal — building epistemic capacity rather than managing epistemic ecosystems — retains its force even when near-term constraints require compromise. We emphasize that calling the failure to provide adequate critical thinking education an epistemic injustice (Fricker, 2007; WHO, 2025) is not a rhetorical move to defer the problem: it is a claim about where the normative burden lies, and on who bears it.

Conclusion

Misinformation and disinformation threaten epistemic autonomy. Here we argued that also most of the approaches that have been developed to address the issues posed by misinformation and disinformation threaten epistemic autonomy. The epistemic paternalism trap arises when interventions are designed to produce clean, accurate information environments by replacing individual reasoning with institutional or algorithmic judgment, in the name of protection. The core issue is not protection itself, but where the intervention is

directed: at the information ecosystem rather than at strengthening the epistemic capacities of the individuals navigating it. The case for a different approach, however, does not depend on a prior commitment to autonomy; it holds equally for those who primarily care about epistemic outcomes. The algorithmic judgment on offer is biased; the alternative, i.e., building people's capacity, is grounded in evidence. Bioethics has a role to play upstream: not only in auditing tools after deployment, but in making the normative choices explicit before the architecture has been built. For example, which conception of autonomy — non-interference, deliberative capacity, epistemic independence — should our tools be designed to support? This decision is not merely a matter of technical implementation and should not be defined primarily by the technical architectural paradigms of tools developed to counter misinformation and disinformation. AI is neither the ultimate weapon against misinformation, nor a neutral arbiter of truth. It can support human judgment — but only if we decide, before building the tools, what kind of judgment we want it to support.

References

Ahlstrom-Vij, K. (2013). *Epistemic Paternalism*. Palgrave Macmillan UK.

<https://doi.org/10.1057/9781137313171>

Basol, M., Roozenbeek, J., Berriche, M., Uenal, F., McClanahan, W. P., & Linden, S. van der.

(2021). Towards psychological herd immunity: Cross-cultural evidence for two prebunking interventions against COVID-19 misinformation. *Big Data & Society*, 8(1), 20539517211013868. <https://doi.org/10.1177/20539517211013868>

Bateman, J., & Jackson, D. (2024, January 31). *Countering Disinformation Effectively: An Evidence-Based Policy Guide*. Carnegie Endowment for International Peace.

<https://carnegieendowment.org/research/2024/01/countering-disinformation-effectively-an-evidence-based-policy-guide>

Beauchamp, T. L., & Childress, J. F. (2013). *Principles of biomedical ethics* (7th ed). Oxford University Press.

Boisseau, É. (2026). Expertise, opacity, and trust in AI systems. *Synthese*, 207(3), 104.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11229-026-05484-2>

Brandolini, A. (2013, January 11). *The bullshit asymmetry: The amount of energy needed to refute bullshit is an order of magnitude bigger than to produce it*. [Tweet]. Twitter.

<https://x.com/ziobrand/status/289635060758507521>

- Broniatowski, D. A., Zhong, W., Simons, J. R., Jamison, A. M., Dredze, M., & Abrams, L. C. (2025). Explaining Twitter's inability to effectively moderate content during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Scientific Reports*, 15(1), 36096. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-025-20033-6>
- Carnat, I. (2024). Human, all too human: Accounting for automation bias in generative large language models. *International Data Privacy Law*, 14(4), 299–314. <https://doi.org/10.1093/idpl/ipae018>
- Christman, J. (2025). Autonomy in Moral and Political Philosophy. In E. N. Zalta & U. Nodelman (Eds), *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (Fall 2025). Metaphysics Research Lab, Stanford University. <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/fall2025/entries/autonomy-moral/>
- Dworkin, G. (1988). *The Theory and Practice of Autonomy*. Cambridge University Press.
- Ecker, U. K. H., Lewandowsky, S., & Chadwick, M. (2020). Can corrections spread misinformation to new audiences? Testing for the elusive familiarity backfire effect. *Cognitive Research: Principles and Implications*, 5(1), 41. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41235-020-00241-6>
- Ecker, U. K. H., Lewandowsky, S., Cook, J., Schmid, P., Fazio, L. K., Brashier, N., Kendeou, P., Vraga, E. K., & Amazeen, M. A. (2022). The psychological drivers of misinformation belief and its resistance to correction. *Nature Reviews Psychology*, 1(1), 13–29. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s44159-021-00006-y>
- EU AI Act, Pub. L. No. 2024/1689 (2024). <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2024/1689/oj>
- Fazio, L. K. (2020). Repetition Increases Perceived Truth Even for Known Falsehoods. *Collabra: Psychology*, 6(1), 38. <https://doi.org/10.1525/collabra.347>
- Ferrario, A., Loi, M., & Viganò, E. (2020). In AI We Trust Incrementally: A Multi-layer Model of Trust to Analyze Human-Artificial Intelligence Interactions. *Philosophy & Technology*, 33(3), 523–539. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13347-019-00378-3>

- Fricker, M. (2007). *Epistemic Injustice: Power and the Ethics of Knowing*. Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780198237907.001.0001>
- Germani, F., & Spitale, G. (2025). Source framing triggers systematic bias in large language models. *Science Advances*, *11*(45), eadz2924. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.adz2924>
- Germani, F., Spitale, G., & Caplan, A. L. (2026). Trump's statements about acetaminophen and the problem of epistemic corrections. *BMJ Evidence-Based Medicine*, bmjebm-2025-114372. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjebm-2025-114372>
- Goddard, K., Roudsari, A., & Wyatt, J. C. (2012). Automation bias: A systematic review of frequency, effect mediators, and mitigators. *Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association : JAMIA*, *19*(1), 121–127. <https://doi.org/10.1136/amiajnl-2011-000089>
- Goldstein, J. A., Chao, J., Grossman, S., Stamos, A., & Tomz, M. (2024). How persuasive is AI-generated propaganda? *PNAS Nexus*, *3*(2), pgae034. <https://doi.org/10.1093/pnasnexus/pgae034>
- Hartmann, D., De Pereira, J. R. L., Streitböcker, C., & Berendt, B. (2025). Addressing the regulatory gap: Moving towards an EU AI audit ecosystem beyond the AI Act by including civil society. *AI and Ethics*, *5*(4), 3617–3638. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43681-024-00595-3>
- Hoes, E., Aitken, B., Zhang, J., Gackowski, T., & Wojcieszak, M. (2024). Prominent misinformation interventions reduce misperceptions but increase scepticism. *Nature Human Behaviour*, *8*(8), 1545–1553. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41562-024-01884-x>
- Jakesch, M., Hancock, J. T., & Naaman, M. (2023). Human heuristics for AI-generated language are flawed. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, *120*(11), e2208839120. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2208839120>
- Levy, N. (2018). Taking responsibility for health in an epistemically polluted environment. *Theoretical Medicine and Bioethics*, *39*(2), 123–141. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11017-018-9444-1>

- Levy, N. (2021). Epistemic Pollution. In N. Levy, *Bad Beliefs* (1st edn, pp. 110–131). Oxford University Press/Oxford. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oso/9780192895325.003.0005>
- Lewandowsky, S., Ecker, U. K. H., Seifert, C. M., Schwarz, N., & Cook, J. (2012). Misinformation and Its Correction: Continued Influence and Successful Debiasing. *Psychological Science in the Public Interest*, *13*(3), 106–131. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1529100612451018>
- Lewandowsky, S., & van der Linden, S. (2021). Countering Misinformation and Fake News Through Inoculation and Prebunking. *European Review of Social Psychology*, *32*(2), 348–384. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10463283.2021.1876983>
- Loru, E., Nudo, J., Di Marco, N., Santirocchi, A., Atzeni, R., Cinelli, M., Cestari, V., Rossi-Arnaud, C., & Quattrocioni, W. (2025). The simulation of judgment in LLMs. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, *122*(42), e2518443122. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2518443122>
- Matheson, J. (2024). The Philosophy of Epistemic Autonomy: Introduction to Special Issue. *Social Epistemology*, *38*(3), 267–273. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02691728.2024.2335623>
- Mosleh, M., Martel, C., Eckles, D., & Rand, D. (2021). Perverse Downstream Consequences of Debunking: Being Corrected by Another User for Posting False Political News Increases Subsequent Sharing of Low Quality, Partisan, and Toxic Content in a Twitter Field Experiment. *Proceedings of the 2021 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems, CHI '21*, 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3411764.3445642>
- Motoki, F., Pinho Neto, V., & Rodrigues, V. (2024). More human than human: Measuring ChatGPT political bias. *Public Choice*, *198*(1–2), 3–23. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11127-023-01097-2>
- Nyhan, B. (2021). Why the backfire effect does not explain the durability of political misperceptions. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, *118*(15), e1912440117. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1912440117>

- Nyhan, B., & Reifler, J. (2010). When Corrections Fail: The Persistence of Political Misperceptions. *Political Behavior*, 32(2), 303–330. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11109-010-9112-2>
- O'Neill, O. (2002). *Autonomy and Trust in Bioethics*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511606250>
- Pearson, H., & Ledford, H. (2025). Trump links autism and Tylenol: Is there any truth to it? *Nature*, 646(8083), 13–14. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-025-02876-1>
- Pennycook, G., & Rand, D. G. (2019). Lazy, not biased: Susceptibility to partisan fake news is better explained by lack of reasoning than by motivated reasoning. *Cognition*, 188, 39–50. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cognition.2018.06.011>
- Qazi, I. A., Ali, A., Khawaja, A. U., Akhtar, M. J., Sheikh, A. Z., & Alizai, M. H. (2026). Automation Bias in Large Language Model-Assisted Diagnostic Reasoning among Physicians Trained in AI Literacy—A Randomized Clinical Trial. *NEJM AI*, 3(5), A0a2501001. <https://doi.org/10.1056/A0a2501001>
- Quattrocioni, W., Capraro, V., & Perc, M. (2025). *Epistemological Fault Lines Between Human and Artificial Intelligence* (arXiv:2512.19466). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2512.19466>
- Readelli, S., Spitale, G., & Germani, F. (2026). *The Structural Fingerprints of Disinformation: A Content-Agnostic Framework*.
- Redaelli, S., Biller-Andorno, N., Gloeckler, S., Brown, J., Spitale, G., & Germani, F. (2025). Mastering critical thinking skills is strongly associated with the ability to recognize fakeness and misinformation. *Frontiers in Education*, 10, 1577692. <https://doi.org/10.3389/feduc.2025.1577692>
- Roozenbeek, J., Linden, S. van der, & Nygren, T. (2020). Prebunking interventions based on “inoculation” theory can reduce susceptibility to misinformation across cultures. *Harvard Kennedy School Misinformation Review*, 1(2). <https://doi.org/10.37016//mr-2020-008>

Rozado, D. (2024). The political preferences of LLMs. *PLOS ONE*, *19*(7), e0306621.

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0306621>

Saeidnia, H. R., Jahani, S., Ghiasi, N., & Keshavarz, H. (2026). Generative AI and health misinformation: Production, propagation, and mitigation—a systematic review. *BMC Public Health*, *26*(1), 693. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-025-26148-9>

Saju, L., Bleier, A., Lasser, J., & Wagner, C. (2025). *Facts are Harder Than Opinions—A Multilingual, Comparative Analysis of LLM-Based Fact-Checking Reliability* (arXiv:2506.03655). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2506.03655>

Siegel, H. (1990). *Educating Reason: Rationality, Critical Thinking, and Education*. Routledge.

Skitka, L. J., Mosier, K. L., & Burdick, M. (1999). Does automation bias decision-making? *International Journal of Human-Computer Studies*, *51*(5), 991–1006. <https://doi.org/10.1006/ijhc.1999.0252>

Skurnik, I., Yoon, C., Park, D. C., & Schwarz, N. (2005). How Warnings about False Claims Become Recommendations. *Journal of Consumer Research*, *31*(4), 713–724. <https://doi.org/10.1086/426605>

Spitale, G., Biller-Andorno, N., & Germani, F. (2023). AI model GPT-3 (dis)informs us better than humans. *Science Advances*, *9*(26), eadh1850. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.adh1850>

Spitale, G., Germani, F., Biller-Andorno, N., Varaidzo Machiri, S., von Harbou, K., Emiroglu, N., Reeder, J., & Reis, A. A. (2026). Why ethics in social listening and infodemic management matters for public health. *BMJ Public Health*, *4*(1), e003652. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjph-2025-003652>

Sun, Y., & Xie, J. (2026). Do Heuristic Cues Affect Misinformation Sharing? Evidence From a Meta-Analysis. *Journalism & Mass Communication Quarterly*, *103*(1), 249–272. <https://doi.org/10.1177/10776990241284597>

- Taguchi, K., Matsoso, P., Drieco, R., Nunes, T. da S., Soliman, A., & Tangcharoensathien, V. (2023). Effective Infodemic Management: A Substantive Article of the Pandemic Accord. *JMIR Infodemiology*, 3(1), e51760. <https://doi.org/10.2196/51760>
- US Department of Health and Human Services. (2025, September 22). *President Trump, Secretary Kennedy Announce Bold Actions to Tackle Autism Epidemic* [Press Release]. <https://www.hhs.gov/press-room/hhs-trump-kennedy-autism-initiatives-leucovorin-tylenol-research-2025.html>
- Van Der Linden, S. (2022). Misinformation: Susceptibility, spread, and interventions to immunize the public. *Nature Medicine*, 28(3), 460–467. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-022-01713-6>
- Van Der Linden, S., Roozenbeek, J., & Compton, J. (2020). Inoculating Against Fake News About COVID-19. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 11, 566790. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.566790>
- Vinay, R., Spitale, G., Biller-Andorno, N., & Germani, F. (2025). Emotional prompting amplifies disinformation generation in AI large language models. *Frontiers in Artificial Intelligence*, 8. <https://doi.org/10.3389/frai.2025.1543603>
- Vosoughi, S., Roy, D., & Aral, S. (2018). The spread of true and false news online. *Science*, 359(6380), 1146–1151. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aap9559>
- Wardle, C., & Derakshan, H. (2017). *Information disorder: Toward an interdisciplinary framework for research and policy making*. <https://edoc.coe.int/en/media/7495-information-disorder-toward-an-interdisciplinary-framework-for-research-and-policy-making.html>
- WHO. (2025). *Social listening in infodemic management for public health emergencies*. World Health Organization. <https://www.who.int/publications/b/67856>
- Williamson, P. (2016). Take the time and effort to correct misinformation. *Nature*, 540(7632), 171–171. <https://doi.org/10.1038/540171a>

Wood, T., & Porter, E. (2019). The Elusive Backfire Effect: Mass Attitudes' Steadfast Factual Adherence. *Political Behavior*, 41(1), 135–163. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11109-018-9443-y>

Ye, S., Attali, D., Ghazi, M., Cachia, A., Cassotti, M., & Borst, G. (2026). Systematic review and meta-analysis of the evidence for an illusory truth effect and its determinants. *Nature Communications*, 17(1), 3270. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-026-70041-x>

Zagzebski, L. T. (2012). *Epistemic Authority: A Theory of Trust, Authority, and Autonomy in Belief*. Oxford University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780199936472.001.0001>